

MADANIY XABARDORLIKNI OSHIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH | xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

MADANIY XABARDORLIKNI OSHIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH

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«Og‘ir ekologik sharoitga qaramasdan, mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotiga munosib hissa qo‘shib kelayotgan Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini, uning barcha shahar, tuman va ovullarini kompleks tarzda rivojlantirish, mehnatkash va matonatli, oqko‘ngil va bag‘rikeng qoraqalpoq elining hayotini obod va farovon etishga har qachongidan ham ustuvor ahamiyat qaratamiz.

Bizning oliy va ezgu maqsadimiz – birgalikdagi fidokorona mehnatimiz bilan Yangi O‘zbekiston tarkibida Yangi Qoraqalpog‘istonni bunyod etishdir.»

Sh.M.MIRZIYOYEV
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti

Prezident: “Bu ko‘prik o‘zbek va qoraqalpoq xalqlari o‘rtasidagi og‘zibirlik va hamkorlik ko‘prigidir”.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini Xorazm viloyati bilan bog‘lovchi ko‘prik. Asosiy qo‘shma ko‘prikning uzunligi 413 metr bo‘lib, eni 8 metr; har bir oraliq‘i 66 metrni tashkil qiladi. Uning 7 ta ustuni 6 ta oraliqqa o‘rnatilgan.

KIRISH

2024-yilning 17–18-may kunlari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi Xo‘jayli tumanida o‘tkazilgan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy madaniy, etnografik va ekologik merosini keng jamoatchilikka tanitishda hamda turizm infratuzilmalarini mustahkamlashda muhim qadam bo‘ldi

Anjumanning asosiy maqsadi Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozoriga olib kirish va madaniy xabardorlikni oshirishdir. Qoraqalpog‘iston o‘zining tarixiy boyliklari, arxeologik yodgorliklari va o‘ziga xos tabiiy manzaralari bilan dunyo sayyohlarini jalb etadigan katta jozibadorlikka ega. Bu hududda jahon madaniy va tabiiy merosi obyektlariga mansub ko‘plab joylar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning aksariyati turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishga asos bo‘ladi.

Xususan, Qoraqalpog‘istondagi insoniyat tamaddunidan hikoya qiluvchi arxeologik yodgorliklar bisyor. Hozirgi kunda Qoraqalpog‘istonda 300 dan ortiq arxeologik obyektlar mavjud bo‘lib, ulardan eng mashhurlari – Ko‘hna Urganch, Tupraqal‘a, Ellikqal‘a va Ayoqal‘a hududlaridagi qadimiy manzillardir. Bular, o‘z navbatida, sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirib, hududning turistik imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha muhokamalar o‘tkazildi. Birinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalariga bag‘ishlanib, mahalliy infratuzilmalarni takomillashtirish hamda turizm xizmatlarini kengaytirish bo‘yicha takliflar ishlab chiqildi. Ikkinchi yo‘nalishda etnografik turizmni rivojlantirish, xususan, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni targ‘ib etish va milliy madaniy boyliklarni namoyish qilish masalalari muhokama qilindi. Uchinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari orqali targ‘ib qilish masalalariga bag‘ishlandi.

Ushbu anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish yo‘lida muhim qadamdir. Turizm, madaniy meros va ekologik yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan taklif va tavsiyalar hududni xalqaro turistik xaritada o‘z o‘rniga ega bo‘lishiga yordam beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi tarixiy, madaniy va tabiiy boyliklarga ega hudud sifatida nafaqat O‘zbekiston, balki butun Markaziy Osiyoda alohida o‘rin tutadi. Bu hududni «ochiq osmon ostidagi arxeologik muzey» deb atash mumkin, chunki bu yerda qadimiy Xorazm madaniyatining markazi bo‘lgan Qoraqalpog‘istonda nafaqat arxeologik meros, balki etnografik va ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish uchun katta imkoniyatlar mavjud.

Qoraqalpog‘istonda o‘tkaziladigan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro anjuman ana

shunday salohiyatni namoyon etish va rivojlantirish maqsadida tashkil etilgan. Anjuman doirasida turli olimlar, tadqiqotchilar va xalqaro ekspertlar ishtirokida ekologik barqarorlik va madaniy merosni saqlash masalalari muhokama qilinib, zamonaviy turizm yo‘nalishlaridagi ilmiy-nazariy takliflar ishlab chiqildi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha quyidagi muhokamalar o‘tkazildi:

- *Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalari;*
- *Etnografik turizmni tashkil etishning asosiy xususiyatlari;*
- *Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida targ‘ib qilishning zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari.*

Anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida ekologik va etnografik turizm nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga tanitishga yordam berishi olgari surildi.

Anjumanda xalqaro institutlar vakillarining qatnashishi bejiz emas. Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy tarixi va Xorazm madaniyati bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan qadimiy yodgorliklar va arxeologik topinmalar bu hududni nafaqat tarixchilar, arxeologlar uchun, balki turistlar uchun ham jozibadorligini oshirib boradi.

Masalan, Ko‘kcha III qabristoni – qadimgi bronza davri madaniyatiga oid yodgorlik bo‘lib, millioddan avvalgi XIII-XI asrlarga oid, deb taxmin qilinadi. Bu madaniyatlar ko‘p asrlar davomida bir-biri bilan hamkorlikda yashaganini va turli etnik guruhlarning madaniy merosini o‘zida mujassam etganini ko‘rsatadi.

Masalan, S.P. Tolstov¹ tomonidan o‘rganilgan Tazabagyab madaniyatlari ham Qoraqalpog‘istonning arxeologik salohiyatining muhim qismi bo‘lib, ularni o‘rganish natijasida bronza davrining ikki madaniyati bir vaqtning o‘zida mavjud bo‘lgani ma‘lum bo‘lgan. Bu esa hududda turli tarixiy etnik va madaniy jarayonlar sodir bo‘lganidan dalolat beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘istonning ushbu yodgorliklari va arxeologik manzillari sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirishi mumkin.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasining turizm salohiyati juda katta bo‘lib, uni jahon turizm bozoriga zamonaviy marketing vositalari orqali chiqarish imkoni bor. Bu borada ekologik va etnografik turizm muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu turizm yo‘nalishlari nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki uning madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga yoyishda ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mazkur anjuman, ayniqsa, Qoraqalpog‘istonning kelgusi turizm salohiyatini mustahkamlashda, asosiy yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan takliflarni keng tatbiq qilishda omil bo‘lib, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish va yangi turizm xizmatlarini joriy qilishga, hudud aholisi uchun yetarli darajada doimiy va mavsumiy daromadli ish o‘rinlari yaratishga xizmat qiladi.

1 <https://ensiklopediya.uz>

II-SHO'BA

Etnografik turizmni
tashkil etishning
asosiy xususiyatlari

TASTE AND TRADITION: EXPLORING POTENTIALS OF RURAL TOURISM IN KARAKALPAKSTAN

Dr. Hrvoje Ivan Horvat

Lead Technical Specialist, UNDP Uzbekistan

In recent years, the conversation surrounding Karakalpakstan has often been shadowed by the history of the Aral Sea disaster. This narrative, while rooted in a significant environmental misfortune, can obscure the region's resilient spirit, vibrant culture, and untapped potential. It's time to rewrite this story, emphasizing hope, recovery, and the unique attributes that make Karakalpakstan a compelling destination.

The region's traditional cuisine, music, and arts, paired with its rich history, offer a vibrant tapestry that can captivate tourists. By promoting these cultural treasures, we not only honor the past but also pave the way for a brighter future.

Lessons from Croatia

Croatia, known for its remarkable coastline, has successfully developed sustainable rural tourism in its inland areas, which were never considered overly interesting for visiting. Initially overlooked, these regions have now become fashionable destinations. This transformation offers valuable lessons that, with creativity and perseverance, typically non-traditional tourist areas can thrive.

Namely, at the onset of internet sites and services, some Croatian families in remote, arid regions began to redecorate their homes and offer them online to tourists. Despite lacking experience in tourism and having poor infrastructure, these areas attracted visitors seeking authentic experiences.

The Croatian government recognized the momentum and started supporting these initiatives by providing credit lines for the reconstruction and redecoration of homes, with favourable terms for touristic activities. The local government and cities started investing in local branding, infrastructure, organizing local events and festivals, opening dedicated websites, establishing touristic info points, printing brochures, and more. It was recognized that certain travellers prefer the tranquillity and authenticity of rural destinations over crowded tourist hotspots. Today, almost two decades since the beginning of these changes, those areas have a stable and thriving tourism offer.

Attractive Offer is the Key

This example shows that even without a prior tourism industry, areas can attract guests if they offer unique and authentic experiences. Similarly, Karakalpakstan's development requires collaborative efforts between the government and local communities. By offering financial support and promoting local culture, the potential for sustainable tourism can be unlocked. Karakalpakstan's picturesque villages, historical sites, and local festivals could provide a rich offer that can appeal to touristic markets and create a thriving tourism sector.

Tourism can flourish anywhere if there is a compelling and interesting offer. For Karakalpakstan, this means investing in the knowledge and skills of local

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi

Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана

Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

communities, enhancing hospitality services, and promoting local attractions. Support from various sectors, including education, finance, and community development, is essential to create a robust tourism industry.

Key Future Steps

However, to ensure the success of sustainable rural tourism in Karakalpakstan, we must adhere to several key principles and actions:

- Establishing a clear vision and guiding principles is paramount. This vision should reflect a commitment to sustainability, cultural preservation, and community engagement, providing a roadmap for all stakeholders.
- Investing in capacity building and engaging local communities are essential steps. Training programs, workshops, and community forums can empower residents to take active roles in tourism development, ensuring that the benefits are widely shared.
- Supporting sustainable agricultural practices can enhance the appeal of rural areas. By promoting eco-friendly farming techniques, we can ensure the longevity of natural resources and provide tourists with fresh, locally sourced products.
- Preserving cultural heritage is vital for attracting tourists interested in authentic experiences. Initiatives to protect and promote traditional arts and crafts will enrich the tourism offer and foster pride among local communities.
- Effective marketing and promotion are crucial to putting Karakalpakstan on the tourism map. Developing a strong brand identity and leveraging digital platforms can attract global attention and drive visitor numbers.
- Visiting other countries to learn from their successes and mistakes can provide valuable insights. By studying best practices in sustainable tourism, Karakalpakstan can avoid common pitfalls and implement proven strategies.
- Infrastructure development is necessary to support tourism growth. Improving transportation, accommodation, and amenities will enhance the visitor experience and encourage longer stays.

Karakalpakstan stands at a crossroads. By shifting the narrative from past disasters to future possibilities, celebrating its rich culture, and fostering government and community support, the region can unlock its tourism potential. Sustainable rural tourism offers a path to economic growth and cultural preservation, ensuring that Karakalpakstan's story is one of resilience, innovation, and hope. Let's embrace this vision and work together to create a thriving and sustainable future for Karakalpakstan.

TOSHKENT DAVLAT IQTISODIYOTI UNIVERSITETI TOMONIDAN TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO‘YICHA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN ISHLAR HAQIDA MA‘LUMOT

26–28 -may
“Ralli Mo‘ynoq-2023”
avtoralli bo‘yicha O‘zbekiston chempionati
o‘tkazildi

TURISTLAR
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Mahalliy – 80 ta

30-may
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TURISTLAR
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1–2-iyun
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yoshlar festivali Ellikqal’a
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TURISTLAR
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Qoraqalpog‘iston
Respublikasiga
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12–15-iyun
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Respublikasi
Xo‘jayli va
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TURISTLAR
Mahalliy – 48 ta

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“Innoweek-2023”
startap loyihalar tanlovi
g‘oliblari Qoraqalpog‘iston
Respublikasidagi tarixiy
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bilan tanishdi

TURISTLAR
Mahalliy – 40 ta

9-iyun
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Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

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